

The Grand Architecture of Life

George Kevin Po

Bachelor of Science in Computer Engineering Graduate in the Philippines

Abstract:- What is life? What makes it special? What makes up our own atoms? What holds it together? If we are made out of atoms, what makes atoms hold together while we move? If an atom's quantum gravity is the only one holding together all atoms, why could we move when objects cannot? And why do we have consciousness if that is the case? This question was always what I ask myself after watching all possible documentaries and reading Facebook posts in some science forums (since there are only limited forums which have active members on it) about atoms and stuff. Aren't we better off like other objects if we are made out of atoms, just like gases, solids or liquids?

Keywords:- Dark Energy, Quantum Realm, Consciousness, Reality, Mind, Energy Transformations, Black Hole.

I. INTRODUCTION

Those at the abstract are the main questions which I was curious about one day when I was struck with slight sickness of which I am now cured of it, as the only way for me to stop it all was to bring out my own best and all the scientific theories that I could come up with. All of this theories are just purely thought experiments, if I would like to note of my research. As I play fair, I would like to declare of my intention which is why I am writing a bit about myself, as there are no other things that I could have said. I know that making this research paper would be highly embarrassing, but the thought of not publishing my research leaves me no other choice, as both a reward to my hard work and passion even though through the circumstance I was in when I made the theories. Please note that during when I made my theories, my knowledge of science was still at the year 2010, more or less. After reading many sources of information, it had enlightened me, which is also why this research paper is already revised in a way. That these theories are already made simplified due to the authors character and for the readers as well, as well as the theories were made original.

As mentioned, all this are just Thought Experiments using all available logic, imagination, and knowledge. There are just many mysteries in life which has yet to be solved, or is unknown even to science, where many would most likely seek towards the supernatural for answers to the unknown. And not long before I made this paper, I made a sort of survey towards some science forums on Facebook, which held many expected results. That about more or less 90% of people believe or learn from many sources, that life is basically biological, nothing more or less. The rest of the participants would just be from rude skeptics to concerned people, which those concerned people would not brag or answer what they don't really know. And thus, in this paper,

I will clarify or answer those questions which bothers many scientists and philosophers.

II. ANALYSIS, DISCUSSION AND FINDINGS

To start off the discussion, let me start off with a story or general theory, on how life has basically started:

“Once there were 2 kinds of particles in a black blank space in the first point in time, particles and anti particles, where like particles repel and opposite particles attract, just like in electromagnetism. But with their very little tiny space in a point in time, those particles just had no other choice but to fuse altogether, thus forming what we all know as the atom. And from the fusion of such quantities, the energy produced was just too great to contain, that a big bang happened from the one small space. The result was that the particles both fused into atoms and separated (fission) into smaller particles before fusing again, which was also very chaotic at first, and which the space around them grew as well. Though as the space grew, it only grew so much before shrinking again to the allowed space needed, in time, and thus the process continues over and over again in short periods of time. The process of which like on how the heart first pumps blood into the system for the very first time, or on how a spark starts, slowly but surely, until the energy generated would be enough.

Before long, as the chaos within such space widened so very much, that the product of fusion of atoms was the first ever matter in this universe. From there, the dark energy along with all the other energies, shaped everything up just like a program. Then after billions of years of chaos, mixing, making and sorting out everything, the dark energy finally shaped up all the needed galaxies. Galaxies were formed from some of the atoms that had burst out from the big bang around the whole universe, then the dark energy went unto forming many more stars and mixing elements to form planets and other space debris. And as the process goes on, and in a short time of fusion reactions in those suns, thus created black holes. And from the electromagnetic force the black hole creates, its own gravity is then generated to pull more particles around other spaces or other smaller black holes near it. And of course, Dark Energy would also have the random program which would slowly drift apart those Black Holes from other stars and planets.

In time, as planets or stars are then formed from all the chaos and continuous processes, both planet and star then exhibit gravity to make the either other planets or moon. Then after all the chaos has been settled in any planet, the planet cools down before beginning the next set of processes at the planet, which is still having atoms slowly combine

overtime, thus creating life. Life is not just made directly, as it is the result of random continuous combinations from all the atoms present on the planets surface at that time, before finally achieving the random results of many types of life in any planet. From the energies of the planet, from the stars (plasma made from the sun), from the universe itself (the leftover energies made from the processes it went through), and from Dark Energy (or quantum energies), some sort of program was then made from all the processes from the very beginning of time up to the present. Which we also might call, the brain, even though small it may be seen in that time (single cell organisms). Which those organisms would slowly evolve themselves in time, and due to its harsh environment. And from that life itself, a series of combinations and extinctions took place (survival of the fittest and constant evolution) which evolves such life into the complex life presently available in time.

As soon as the brain was made, as the first few species was also made, the dark energy would now also program or make all species to “spread out” or multiply which is true in other species as well. So the brain of the female, after receiving the signals of reproduction and the sperm of the male (which is the key ingredient to start the process), would then trigger signals within the body to help with the making of the new life inside of the female. Those neuron or quantum signals from the brain would then get atoms from its surroundings (inside the womb), including the vitamins and minerals being absorbed by the female or mother, to form the new life or the baby after some time in the womb.”

Thus, the “Genesis Theory” is made. Then on the following pages, I will then discuss further about everything else.

➤ *The Macro Scale*

So far, we all know that the Earth rotates around the sun along with other planets, as the sun rotates along the supermassive Black Hole at the center of the galaxy along with other stars and systems, and as the galaxy slowly and randomly moves around the universe. And that this universe has many other kinds of stuff, like stars, planets, Black Holes, White Holes (if there may be), and many others. According to the red shift of planets as we look at the stars, the other galaxies are really very far because of dark energy, as far as we know. But that is also cause dark energy programs the galaxies to go further away from other galaxies, while it also prevents a galaxy from dissipating itself. Meaning that all the planetary systems in a galaxy would stay within the galaxy, as it courses through the universe. Cause if dark energy is only there to push galaxies away from each other, the big crunch would have already happened with or without us even knowing it, in this randomly unpredictable universe. Where the big crunch is a theory which the universe will end by the collapse of everything, even atoms, as dark energy will continue to push galaxies farther away from each other. Though it may be true that humans and all of matter has a beginning and an end, it doesnt mean everything else that isnt made of matter has it. Also, Gravity is only the product of the interactions of when any planet or star was first formed in time. Of which gravity is the result of the

interactions between dark energy, electromagnetism, strong and weak nuclear forces.

Space cant be described fully without time, as space is relative to time, this the term spacetime. Where space is the 3 dimensions in which everything is moving on, where both space and time cant be seen, just felt through the 5 senses. Where with all 3 (dark energy, space, and time), they shape all of reality, where matter and everything else are just secondary. And to the question about time, I also think that the past, present, and future are existing simultaneously. Like time itself is just a single line in space, or just a single string. We don't know just how long the string is, nor its thickness, just that we are in the web or tree known as the multiverse. Its true that the future cant be without the present, as the present cant be without the past, but I think that everything also happens for a reason. Why? Aside from it being the most logical to think, causality and entropy are maintained in the universe, thus a certain balance in the whole program is achieved. In regards with time, I would like to categorize about 5 types of time in this universe:

- Universal Time, in which this is the time for galaxies on their journey across the universe.
- Galactic Time, in which this is the time for stars, star systems, and other heavenly bodies on their journey across the galaxy.
- Planetary Time, in which this is the time for all living organisms and objects on their journey on that planet.
- Organic Time, in which this is the time for all cells inside the body of a living organism on their journey across the available lifetime for that organism.
- Quantum Time, in which this is the time for all atoms and subatomic particles on their activity throughout its entire lifetime, whether the atoms may be fused with another or separated through fission.

➤ *Reality*

According to string theory, the universe is made up of many strings of existence, which makes up our reality(ies). And according to relativity, spacetime is like a sheet of paper in space, holding the planets in its place as it rotates around the sun or star. Thus, I think that both theories can relate with each other, where reality is made up of multiple sheets called spacetime. As there are also many different strings or sheets of spacetime, there are also many different realities or universes in across space and time, in which we call the multiverse. In which the multiverse is also being maintained or held together by dark energy as well, where dark energy keeps the order of all things, from order to entropy of everything. Also along with dark matter, which is theorized to also hold all realities together, as dark energy manages everything. Since as the universe is like a giant neural network, or can be similar to it, one can also assume that many other realities are like many other neural networks packed in the almost infinite space. With all these factors, one may also assume that the universe is like a giant Yggdrasil, but with many more branches than maybe predicted. Since the universe is also born from many random instances after all. Many assume that reality exists because of us as an observer, but what of blind people? What are their realities? And what of the other planets and stars that we see

beyond our skies? Does this mean those planets have aliens on them, so that they can also help manifest the reality within that planet or star system? Highly unlikely. As reality exists with or without us, as spacetime would as well. An example of spacetime is a film projector: the projector is time unfolding, while the whole reel is the space all of matter is occupying. And an example of the multiverse is like a droplet of water: as the water drops to the pond, it then creates ripples throughout the surface of the water, where the ripples also intersect with each other as time goes by with each droplet.

As for time travel, due to the multiverse theory, it may be possible to go to the past nor future. But the question is: “will you still be able to go back? Even if you might fix things that you have done in the past?” The answer to that is a no, only cause of the multiverse theory. Like if one would go to the past and edit some things that has happened, the most likely to happen is that that point in time would branch out, to become another timeline and to another future either desirable or not. Well, it may not be possible to travel through time physically, since nothing can withstand while travelling at the speed of light. The best ships or planes that could ever fly is around Mach 6, which is the USAF X-15 experimental jet plane. Thus its not possible to travel towards the future, unless if we could only open up an artificial Wormhole, and in space. Since opening up a Wormhole on a planet might mean the end of life in a way, as it will suck everything, and as its not like opening the main gate to any palace or something. Also, its not possible to travel to the past, as you would also need to rewind all of time in the universe just to get to that time period. Which is all next to impossible, since you would need to harness the universe first in order to make it all happen. But a question will rise: “what exactly will happen if one goes back in time using all the energy from the universe, or at least some of it? Will that current timeline be gone forever?” I presume that since the energy from the universe will be used to open a Wormhole in space, everything near the Wormhole will eventually be destroyed as well, which the damage to that timeline might depend.

➤ *Black Holes*

As far as we know, Black Holes comes from the death of stars or suns with or without a system around it, but it would also depend on the type of star and on its size. So with massive stars, at the end of their cycle or life, they would basically go supernova before becoming Black Holes themselves. And little is known on their true nature, but I think that we might be relying too much on the math. Then there are also Wormholes (or Einstein-Rosen Bridge), where it was mathematically proven to exist and not yet seen or visually proven, though both holes are indistinguishable as both are dark in both nature and color. And that Black Holes have mass, as it also absorbs everything in its path. Though I think that Wormholes are actually inside Black Holes, basically making Black Holes an actual hole in spacetime, where it cycles all energy and matter throughout the multiverse and maybe back to this one. And have anyone also ever wondered why any of the “End Theories” hasn’t happened yet? Aside from the math, as math isnt always

absolute, we have not yet sought out some relation with nature itself such as with us humans or towards other things in life. An example of black holes are like after the blast from explosives: after the blast from any explosive device on any fragile surface or not, it will eventually create a hole on that surface towards the other side (if any), thus somewhat connecting those two points of space in time.

➤ *Energy Transformations*

As far as I have already theorized, dark energy is the main program in which it maintains the order of everything in the universe, from atoms to galaxies. But just how does dark energy cycle itself? Or what does energy transform into if it cant be made or destroyed? As dark energy is the force in the universe that maintains the order of the quantum realm and of the galaxies around the universe, its also another kind of energy, though its undetectable through normal and present methods. First we have the sun, which generates enough energy (from fusion reaction) to sustain life for all planets in its system as best as possible. Then the sun will provide energy and nutrients for all plant life on earth, as this is as far as we know that contains life, unlike in other planets. Some animals will then eat the plants, and some animals will eat those other animals, and provide nutrients for the ground through their feces. Of course, the plants will also provide the Earth with energy as well, converting photons or solar energy into nutrients for the ground. Which in turn, the Earth can then provide support for everything else on it, like providing a cycle for water, a cycle for wind or air (through the Earths rotation), and providing enough energy for the cycle of the Earths core. Which includes lightning, where its also generated from the interaction with particles in the sky, and energy is struck back towards the ground or towards other particles in the sky. Then as energy will be spent from doing all that work, the just where does such energy go? I theorize that all that energy will go back towards the dark energy (or quantum energy) no matter how small or unseen it may be, which it will also help provide the sun with enough energy to sustain itself, and for the sun to do work (fusion reaction) as well. Though as the cycle goes on, just where does all that extra unseen energy go towards? I theorize that somewhere in space, there are Black Holes which will suck all that energy, along with other energy and matter along its way. In order to recycle it, towards all of the Multiverse, and to transform back to dark energy. Just as the laws of thermodynamics would state, that energy cant be made or destroyed, just transformed.

➤ *The Mind*

The Brain is truly a mystery, but when you only look at it with a complicated outlook. As the brain is a dark energy generator, which is also why it can also be interfered with any other energy. And as photons are also energy, in which it has dual properties of being both a particle and a wave, thus any type of energy can also interfere with neural activity if being exposed to it. Like electrocution, loud music, energies above or below the infrared spectrum, and many more. Which is why when it comes to the mind, its possible to interfere with neural activity and control it to do some things. Like mind control for one, where one can just expose the subject with the right quantum frequency and link both minds

directly or one way, and control the subject directly or through a way. The way to control someone through a mind control machine is to link ones mind towards the subject, where one way connection would require one to have a visual on the subject and send commands to the subjects brain, through quantum frequencies or frequencies we normally cant hear. Its not that we cant hear them, such signals are just so weak for our minds to translate normally. Just why do people feel some effects from every other frequencies anyways? There is also the possibility of a mind transfer, where you directly exchange both minds or mix them, or to fully transfer ones mind towards the subject. Though in both mind transfer and in mind control, there would be a possibility for mind exchange or transfer, so its advised to not control the subject for too long. This is because neural energy or dark energy inside ones mind is still energy, thus energy is transformed towards each other or towards the subject. And its also possible to send ones neural energy through time, meaning that the only way to travel through time is to take ones mind through time. Since if there would be a time machine of any sort, the best it would do is to open a Wormhole, opening a short tunnel through spacetime at more than the speed of light. Thus destroying the body, and leaving only the neural energy to travel towards the future.

➤ *Consciousness*

The topics behind the other cycles of life was already discussed in energy transformations, but the question for life on Earth remains, on how are we very different from objects? Much less, just lumps of meat? Yes, all living organisms are just lumps of meat, which is no different from any object. But the fact that we have consciousness, or at least the thought of it as according to the majority, makes us very different from just being lumps of meat. In the bible, in the book of genesis, man was made on the 7th day, which is also the last to be made from out of all of creation. This is because of the brain. After the making of single celled organisms from out of all the available resources and materials on Earth, those cells fused and multiplied before fusing gain with other cells, where the process goes on for billions of years. Until the first few creatures came into the picture, where all life came from the sea, just like how babies are made inside the embryo. Then came even more complex fusion and multiplication of many more species, to evolve from their basic forms towards even more complex and highly evolved forms. Where other new species would eventually go towards land, to evolve even further, and thus finally evolve into the living organisms we all know today. Which such highly complicated process of evolution would also evolve the brain, into becoming the living creatures that we all know today.

But where does consciousness come from out of all that evolution? As per the answers from others, consciousness comes from the highly complicated and random interactions from both instinct and intelligence from any living creature. There are also others which say that consciousness comes from the complex interactions from atoms and particles, which is also somewhat true, but kind of lacking in a way. And yes, intelligence may come from the brain, after billions of years of evolution, but what about instinct? I theorize that the brain is also a dark energy generator, which also

generates dark energy from out of all its surroundings, aside from such unseen energy making every living creatures instincts. Yes, consciousness emerges from the brain itself, but just where does consciousness really come from? And thus, the answer is theorized to be dark energy (or quantum energy). Where an example of our brain would be like a quantum computer: where it needs energy to function and a program made of energy to do its programmed functions.

What if all this is not true? Just how can one ever explain what happens inside the Kola Borehole? Where people can also somehow hear the screams of the damned when going towards the bottom of the man made hole. Which also tells that there might be energy entities, as there are living creatures, which are made up of these unseen energy called dark energy. So I ask, what does happen after any living organism die? Though we might already know the concept of why, we just don't believe it, as we complicate ourselves by the visual and mathematical evidences. My theory on this, as we have consciousness, we have a soul. Where a soul is the overall energy or neural energy within the brain. That upon death, the soul will either be attracted to hell, purgatory, or heaven. Heaven is positive dark energy, which is also space, or the darkness beyond our skies. Hell is the planets core, where their souls will help nourish the planets core. And purgatory is the planets surface itself, where its to wander the planet or to be reborn once more. Which upon death of the vessel, will detach itself from the body and go towards the cycle of life one more time, or what we call reincarnation. But how could one prove reincarnation? Just why does some people at times, have memories of their past selves when they were young? Or have some kind of Out of Body Experience where they experience some unexplainable events? Or why can some people see or feel these energy entities when the majority cannot? These questions will always be left on air when being answered by the majority, not believing unless if they experience such themselves.

Just why do we all dream? Dreaming to the majority is the brain shutting down to maintain itself, just like how a computer needs to restart to properly save heavy installations. But sometimes, we remember our dreams, where its like either from or out of this world. My theory is that because our consciousness is also made up from dark energy, we can tap in to see other universes, or that other things influence us during our sleep. Just like how we also have nightmares sometimes, where its probably entropy of the universe or our universe that is influencing us. And why do we sometimes have deja vu? Well, its sometimes an effect of complex interactions with dark energy, us humans, and spacetime. Although events like this would only happen sometimes, totally depending on the randomness of the universe. Where we probably experience the same experience as what we have experienced before, but actually its like a synchronization of sorts with the same person on a parallel universe.

➤ *The Quantum Realm*

From the start of the known universe, there were about 2 kinds of particles, which are the particles and anti particles. All before the complex and chaotic processes made the first

atoms from those 2 particles. Of course, everything would go as programmed by the Dark Energy (or Quantum energy), as the program would all start off from many random processes towards the randomly complex process of what we call the cycle of life. There is also the question on where such particles have really come from from the start, but that can be answered with the fact that it was already there from the start, and nothing can come from nothing. Some would say or don't believe in the quantum, as science or many people would heavily rely on visual and mathematical evidences. But as time goes on, such studies concerning the quantum would be very beneficial to everyone, with or without them knowing that they are now using just one of the products of the studies concerning the quantum.

It is said that in space, there are still other atoms just floating around, which contributes towards the overall complex process of life in the universe. Where those atoms would just lie there in space, or be part of the system in a planet with or without life in it, such as oxygen atoms to name a few. Like when the solar system would float or revolve around the supermassive Black Hole at the center of the galaxy, the planets in our system would also tend to pick up some of these atoms or particles floating in space, as it also tends to leave some other or same atoms or particles behind. Though in the quantum realm, time tends to be really weird, as it can't just be observed through the 5 senses after all. In which phenomenon such as quantum entanglement, is probably possible. Where dark energy is the manager of the order of atoms and subatomic particles, as there are the strong and weak forces. Also that dark matter is the glue or bond to which atoms are held in its place, aside from the strong and weak forces. Just why are all the atoms and particles in the galaxy still intact when the galaxy is also travelling at great speeds across the universe? Thus aside from dark energy managing the atoms, dark matter bonds them real tight, and its also somewhat the glue or the wall towards all the realities in the multiverse. An example of the quantum are like us humans: there are sometimes look alike even though they don't think alike, there are sometimes twins or siblings which instinctively knows sometimes on what to think like or on how to deal with their other twin or sibling, we would decide to do this and that at any or at random times, and many more. In short, just like us, the quantum realm has much entropy or randomness as we do all the time. An example of dark matter would be bee hives: for every reality is represented with a section of the honeycomb, without the honey to make each section stick, each section would only fall apart towards the floor and spoiling both the honey and everything in it.

III. RECOMMENDATIONS

My recommendation is that the only way to know about Dark Energy is to logically analyze its true nature, as no present or maybe future equipment is able to analyze its true nature. As science is now almost at the limit of its capacity, as far as scientific and technological advances are concerned so far. The only things left to discover is for the final frontier, which is space. And space as we know it is filled with Dark Energy and all other matter in the universe. In short, there is

yet a major number of things which we have not accepted that we have already discovered the answer, since we mostly require visual or mathematical proof of its existence or true nature. Well, if one would like evidence of my theories, they may do the below, which would also fall as inhumane:

- Get a dead person's brain
- Make a machine to make the brain work by jump starting it, like jump starting an engine
- Plug the brain inside the machine, so that it can also harvest the energy coming from the brain itself
- Measure the voltage the machine makes

If one follows these 4 steps, then it might be possible to prove these theories above, along with harvesting dark energy. But there is just one problem to this: "would the brain display consciousness once more? Or not?". Although, there is another way, if one would succeed in making a machine which is almost like an EEG (Electro Encephalogram Graph), as the body would sometimes emit some static electricity. Though its not known if the human being harvested with their energy would feel something else, just the feeling of tiredness afterwards, as energy is taken from them directly from the brain. If one would take advantage of that and harness from any human, then we could harness almost unlimited energy. And if one might also be seeking proof, one may also either do the above, do meditation to feel some kind of energy, or to experience an out of body experience.

IV. CONCLUSION

"As the answer is simple, only the solution is complex, specially with humans", that is the saying that I often told myself as it is the most logical approach to any given problem. These theories which are yet unknown is yet to be proven, yet it proves very logical and that the evidences are all around us, which we haven't yet to realize. After all, everything in life is for a purpose, we just have to discover it. So I ask again, if organic life is also made out of atoms, how can they move about without their atoms falling apart unlike in objects? It is because of Dark Energy as the manager of all atoms in the universe, aside from the 4 forces of nature. Which are Gravity, Electromagnetism, Strong force, and Weak force. Please also note that these theory(ies) are maybe not yet complete and maybe still lacking.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Space.com, (2013). Science and Astronomy. What is Dark Energy?: <https://www.space.com/20929-dark-energy.html>
- [2]. Encyclopedia Britannica, (2019). Astronomy. Dark Energy: <https://www.britannica.com/science/dark-energy>
- [3]. Wikipedia. Quantum Realm: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Quantum_realm
- [4]. Space.com. Science and Astronomy. What is String Theory?: <https://www.space.com/17594-string-theory.html>

- [5]. Schoolsobservatory.org. Astronomy. Life Cycle of a Star.:
<https://www.schoolsobservatory.org/learn/astro/stars/cycle>
- [6]. Livescience.com. What are Wormholes?:
<https://www.livescience.com/what-are-wormholes>
- [7]. Livescience.com. What is Multiverse Theory?:
<https://www.livescience.com/multiverse>
- [8]. Can Humans Be Controlled:
<http://www.zo.utexas.edu/courses/thoc/HumanInstincts.html>
- [9]. Psychologydiscussion.net. Human Abilities: Meaning and Nature:
<https://www.psychologydiscussion.net/educational-psychology/human-abilities/human-abilities-meaning-and-nature-educational-psychology/1914>
- [10]. NYAS.org. What Can Science Tell Us About Death?:
<https://www.nyas.org/news-articles/academy-news/is-there-life-after-death/>
- [11]. Forms of Energy: <https://vikaspedia.in/energy/energy-basics/forms-of-energy>
- [12]. How is lightning made:
https://www.nasa.gov/audience/forstudents/k-4/home/F_What_Causes_Lightning_Flash.html
- [13]. Multiwavelength Astronomy. Strong and Weak Nuclear Force: <https://ecuip.lib.uchicago.edu/multiwavelength-astronomy/astrophysics/06.html>
- [14]. What is space?: <https://www.space.com/amp/24870-what-is-space.html>
- [15]. What is Time? A simple explanation:
<https://www.thoughtco.com/what-is-time-4156799>
- [16]. What is spacetime?:
<https://www.livescience.com/amp/space-time.html>
- [17]. What makes mental time travel possible?:
<https://www.apa.org/monitor/oct03/mental>
- [18]. Brainworksneurotherapy.com. What are brainwaves?:
<https://brainworksneurotherapy.com/what-are-brainwaves>
- [19]. WebMD. What are Binaural Beats?:
<https://www.webmd.com/balance/what-are-binaural-beats>
- [20]. Neurosciencenews.com. A New Theory in Physics Claims to Solve the Mystery of Consciousness.
<https://neurosciencenews.com/physics-consciousness-21222/>
- [21]. Flyjetify.com. Fastest Fighter Jet.
<https://www.flyjetify.com/fastest-fighter-jet>
- [22]. Healthline.com. What is EEG?:
<https://www.healthline.com/health/eeg#procedure>